

Bridging Stones and Volcanoes

Can Semantic Modelling, Visualisation, and Little Minions Bridge Archaeology and Geosciences?

Florian Thiery, Fiona Schenk, Peter Thiery

CAA NL-FL | 09-10 Dec 2025 | Stad Brussel | Belgium | 09/12/2025

Session: Data Management & Data Architecture

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

Semantic modelling, visualisation and documentation workflows, plays a significant role in achieving interoperability and reusability ...

... by providing the structured, machine-actionable context for cross-domain integration and reuse of data.

label — **Phaistos disc** (Q465338)

description — inscribed tablet found in Crete
Phaistos Disk | Phaestos Disc
▶ In more languages

Statements

property — **inception** — **value** — **1700 BCE**

earliest date	1700 BCE
latest date	1100 BCE
sourcing circumstances	circa
reason for preferred rank	preferred determination method

qualifiers

rank — **▼ 1 reference**

stated in	Le pouvoir de l'écrit
author	Louis Godart
page(s)	206

opened reference

statement group

rank — **▼ 1400 BCE**

end time	1970
start time	1959

collapsed reference

property — **location of discovery** — **value** — **Phaistos**

statement group

▶ 0 references

+ add reference
+ add value
+ add (statement)

Mtrognitz, CCO, via Wikimedia Commons

Integrating community-driven infrastructures such as the Wikiverse and OpenStreetMap supports also AI systems

fuzzy-sl RDF Modelling Scheme

fuzzy-sl Wikibase Modelling Scheme

LOD

Wikibase

FDO

GIS

OSM

LPG

HIN

EpiDoc

How to “feed” the (CH-) **Federated Knowledge Graph Ecosystem?**

Ogham Stones

Early Medieval Network

Density Map of Ogham Stone Sites (Normalized)

image: Florian Thiery CC BY 4.0, created using OpenAI's DALL-E

Florian Thiery & Peter Thiery, CC BY 4.0

Ogham! 4.-6. AD, early Medieval, “Primitive Irish”

This project is funded by Wikimedia Deutschland e. V. within the Open Science Fellows Program.

OPEN SCIENCE FELLOWS PROGRAM

wmde.org/opensciencefellows

Ogham Stones within the KG Ecosystem

Extract from the Linked Open Ogham Ontology

CIIC 81

- UCC Cork Stone Corridor: #4
- OSM Node: 11071361392
- Wikidata: Q130529871

Open Street Map Contributors, ODBL

© OpenStreetMap contributors, Imagery © Mapbox

↑ Florian Thieri, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

Knoten: CIIC 81 /
UCC 4 (11071361392)

Version #2

added metadata

Bearbeitet vor 19 Tagen von fthiergeo

Änderungssatz #139090380

Standort: 51.8938126, -8.4921198

Tags

historic	ogham_stone
inscription	C[A]SSITT[A7O]S MAQI MU[CO]I CALLITI
moved	yes
moved_to	Q69379477
name	CIIC 81 / UCC 4
project	ogham.link
source	survey
wikidata	Q106680733

↑ Florian Thieri, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

- *Analogue Sources: CIIC, CISP*
- *Linked Open Ogham Data: providing the primary URI*
 - http://lod.ogham.link/data/OghamStone_Squirrel_collection
- *fuzzy-sl Wikibase: coordinates and how they are created*
 - [P4](#)
- *Wikidata: data-hub for external identifiers, e.g., OSM, SMRS, LOD*
 - [P11693](#), [P4057](#), [P2888](#)
- *Semantic Kompakkt Wikibase: 3D Model & Annotations*
 - [P74](#), [P75](#)
- *FactGrid Wikibase for Historians: Inscription & Persons & Words*
 - [P1219](#), [P33](#), [P256](#)
- *TEI/EpiDOC (from the OG(H)AM project)*
- *Open Street Map*
 - [historic=ogham_stone](#)

Use each Repository for data it is “famous” for ...

BARONY OF KINALEA

Upton (97).

At Upton¹, near Inishannon, a stone scored with Ogham writing was found in taking down an old wall, in the year 1837. A promise was made to Windele that the stone would be sent to him, but the promise was never fulfilled, and he heard afterwards that it had been broken up for building purposes. There is no certain guarantee that this and the Lisconigill stone, of which a similar story is told, were any more Ogham than the Youghal stone just mentioned, which was found in similar circumstances.]

BARONY OF KINALMEAKY

81.—Garranes (84).

1869 JRSAL 10 : 260 (Brash). 1911 * *Ivernian* 3 : 73 (Henebry).
On this townland there is an interesting group of earth-works which have recently been examined by excavation. The

C[A]SSITT[A]S MAQI MUOJI CALLITI

¹ There is no townland of this name in the locality.

GARES/1

Corpus Refs: [Macalister/1945:81](#)

Site: [GARES](#)

Discovery: recognised, 1852 Crowley

History: Gippert/Web, Ogham 81: According to Brash, *JRSAL* 10, 1869, 260, the stone was found in a structure called Rath Lisheenagreine, in the townland of Gurranes (sic), parish of Templemartin, 1 mile north of the parish church (the village in question is named "Gurranes" in the Cork U.C. too). A detailed map of the Rath in connection with the larger Rath Lisnacaheragh) is available in S.P. O'Riordan's article in *PRIA* 47-C, 1941-42, 77 ff. -- According to Brash, the stone was discovered by one farmer Crowley 17 years before (the publication of his article in *JRSAL* 10, 1869). Macalister states in *CIIC* that it "has been known since the sixties" and "appears to have come from a souterrain in the group" of 'earth-works' on the townland of Garranes. The first report was made by John Lyons, C.C., Newcestown, Enniskean; Brash's visit took place on 16.12.1868.

The stone was moved to the Museum of the U.C., Cork after Macalister first visited it (at that time it was still 'standing loosely in one of the ditches': *CIIC* 1, 84). In the collection of the U.C., it is assigned no. 17.

Geology: Macalister/1945, 84: 'clayslate'.

Dimensions: 1.75 x 0.48 x 0.18 (converted from Macalister/1945)

Setting: in ground

Location: University College, Cork (Cat: 17)

Gippert/Web, Ogham 81: The stone was moved to the Museum of the U.C., Cork after Macalister first visited it (at that time it was still 'standing loosely in one of the ditches': *CIIC* 1, 84). In the collection of the U.C., it is assigned no. 17.

Form: plain

Condition: complete ; some
Macalister/1945, 84: 'a little chipped'.

Folklore: none

Crosses: none

Decorations: no other decoration

References

- [Gippert/Web](#) Ogham 81 photo, drawing substantial discussion [\[Gippert 81\]](#)
- [Macalister/1945](#) 83-84 photo, drawing concise discussion

GARES/1/1

Readings

Macalister, R.A.S. (1945): [CLASSITT\[AS\]MAQI](#) || |IMUC || |OCJCALLITI

Expansion:

[CLASSITT\[AS\]MAQI MUOJI CALLITI](#)

[Macalister/1945](#) 83-84 reading only

[Ziepler/1981](#) 145-146, 258 reading only

Gippert, J. (1987): [\[CLASSI\]OTT\[AS\]MAQI || |IMUC || |OCJCALLITI](#)

Expansion:

[\[CLASSI\]OTT\[AS\]MAQI MUOJI CALLITI](#)

[Gippert/1985](#) Ogham 81 reading only [\[Gippert 81\]](#)

[Gippert/1985](#) Ogham 81 reading only [\[Gippert 81\]](#)

McManus, D. (1991): [CLASSITT\[AS\]MAQI || |IMUC || |OCJCALLITI](#)

Expansion:

[CLASSITT\[AS\]MAQI MUOJI CALLITI](#)

[Expansion:](#)

[CLASSITT\[AS\]MAQI MUOJI CALLITI](#)

[McManus/1991](#) 63 reading only

Notes

Orientation: vertical up along down.

Position: inc ; aris ; inc ; undecorated

Incision: punched

Macalister/1945, 84: 'bold scores, punched and rubbed'.

Date: 366 - 483 (McManus/1991)

366 - 483 (McManus/1991)

366 - 483 (McManus/1991, 93-94)

Goldicic (ogham)

Ling. Notes: See McManus/1991, 108, 116.

Paleography: none

Legibility: same

Macalister/1945, 84: 'a little chipped, so that some of the vowels are lost, but of the reading there can be no doubt. The notches of the I in the first word are accidentally grouped so as to make AUA, but the engraver's intention cannot be questioned. Preceding the initial C there are some scratches, apparently modern, but in any case of no significance'.

Gippert/Web, Ogham 81: After 55, all in all seven vowel notches are recognizable. There are hardly any traces visible of Macalister's 1A and 2A. Although the two Ls in CALLITI seem to be well separated, we might think of reading CASITI instead.

Lines: 1

Carving errors: 0

Doubtful: no

Names

• [C\[AS\]ITT\[AS\]](#) (Language: Goldicic; Gender: male)

• [C\[AS\]](#) (Language: Goldicic; Gender: male)

• [McManus/1991](#), 111: CALLITI GORAG[?]. Also see p. 112, and 180 note 57.

References

- [Gippert/Web](#) Ogham 81 photo, drawing substantial discussion [\[Gippert 81\]](#)
- [Macalister/1945](#) 83-84 photo, drawing concise discussion
- [Ziepler/1981](#) 145-146, 258 concise discussion

Ogham Stone as CIIC 81 and CISP GARES/1

Define SPARQL query service

```
import os
from SPARQLWrapper import SPARQLWrapper, JSON
import pandas as pd
import geopandas as gpd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from shapely.geometry import Point
import contextily as ctx # For adding OpenStreetMap basemaps
from matplotlib.patches import Patch
from scipy.stats import gaussian_kde
import numpy as np

def querySparql(query):
    sparql = SPARQLWrapper("https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/api/sparql")
    sparql.setQuery(query)
    sparql.setReturnFormat(JSON)
    results = sparql.queryAndConvert()
    return results['results']['bindings']

# Define the GeoJSON file path
geojson_file = os.path.join(os.getcwd(), "gs_ireland_island.geojson") # Adjusted for ...
```


Define the SPARQL Query

```
# SPARQL Query
oghamQuery = """
PREFIX oghamonto: <http://ontology.ogham.link/>
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
SELECT ?item ?label ?geo ?county (count(distinct ?stone) as ?count) WHERE {
?item <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type> <http://ontology.ogham.link/OghamSite> .
?item rdfs:label ?label .
?item <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasGeometry> ?item_geom .
?item_geom <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#asWKT> ?geo .
?item oghamonto:within ?c .
?c a oghamonto:County .
?c rdfs:label ?county .
?stone oghamonto:disclosedAt ?item .
?stone a oghamonto:OghamStone_CIIC .
} GROUP BY ?item ?label ?geo ?county ORDER BY DESC(?count)
"""
```

Visualise the Data as Maps

```
# Filter rows with valid coordinates
df_with_coords = df.dropna(subset=['latitude', 'longitude'])

# Create a GeoDataFrame
gdf = gpd.GeoDataFrame(
    df_with_coords,
    geometry=[Point(xy) for xy in zip(df_with_coords['longitude'], df_with_coords['latitude'])],
    crs="EPSG:4326"
)

# Convert to Web Mercator for OSM basemap
gdf_mercator = gdf.to_crs(epsg=3857)

# Load Ireland boundary from GeoJSON
ireland_boundary = gpd.read_file(geojson_file)
ireland_boundary = ireland_boundary.to_crs(epsg=3857)
```

Fetch Data and Convert to DataFrame

```
# Fetch data using the SPARQL query
sparql_results = querySparql(oghamQuery)

# Convert SPARQL JSON results into a DataFrame
data = []
for result in sparql_results:
    geo = result['geo']['value'] if 'geo' in result else None
    lat, lon = (None, None)
    if geo:
        lon, lat = map(float, geo.replace("POINT(", "").replace(")", "").split())
    data.append({
        "item": result['item']['value'],
        "label": result['label']['value'],
        "county": result['county']['value'],
        "count": int(result.get("count", {}).get("value", 0)),
        "latitude": lat,
        "longitude": lon,
    })

df = pd.DataFrame(data)
df = df.via(https://research-squirrel-engineers.github.io/jupyter-nb-lod/n40kg-ogham-sites-maps)
```

Map of Ogham Stone Sites Grouped by Counties

	item	label	county	count	latitude	longitude
0	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000031	Ballyknock (Ogham Site)	Cork	15	52.026944	-8.071111
1	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000002	Drumlohan (Ogham Site)	Waterford	10	52.163056	-7.468056
2	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000020	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	Kerry	9	52.172500	-10.031111
3	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000149	Kilcoolaght East / Kilhullicaha (Ogham Site)	Kerry	8	52.071944	-9.747222
4	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000170	Knockboy (Ogham Site)	Waterford	8	52.111389	-7.600000
...
191	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000062					
192	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000168					

Map 1: Plot with points coloured by county

```
# Map 1: Plot with points coloured by county
fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 8))
unique_counties = gdf['county'].unique()

# Create a colormap with as many colours as unique counties
cmap = plt.get_cmap('tab20', len(unique_counties))
county_colors = {county: cmap(idx) for idx, county in enumerate(unique_counties)}

patches = []
for county, color in county_colors.items():
    county_data = gdf_mercator[gdf_mercator['county'] == county]
    county_data.plot(ax=ax, color=color, markersize=50, alpha=0.7)
    patches.append(Patch(color=color, label=county)) # Add patch for legend

ctx.add_basemap(ax, source=ctx.providers.OpenStreetMap.Mapnik, zoom=8)
ax.set_axis_off()
plt.title("Map of Ogham Stone Sites Grouped by Counties")
plt.legend(handles=patches, title="Counties", bbox_to_anchor=(1.05, 1), loc='upper left')
plt.show()
```

N40 KG

Item Discussion

Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV (Q74)

Ogham Stone #4 UCC Stone Corridor at UCC Cork

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
British English	No label defined	No description defined	
English	Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	Ogham Stone #4 UCC Stone Corridor at UCC Cork	

Statements

instance of	Archaeological Site	→ 0 references
related to	http://wikidata.org/entity/Q130529671 related to type http://archaeoinformatics.link/ontology#spatialCloseMatch → 0 references	
related to	https://wikibase.semantic-kompaakt.de/entity/Q1247 related to type http://archaeoinformatics.link/ontology#spatialCloseMatch → 0 references	
related to	https://database.bartnrd.de/entity/Q1000294 related to type http://archaeoinformatics.link/ontology#spatialCloseMatch → 0 references	
related to	http://lod.ogham.link/data/Y00000081 related to type http://archaeoinformatics.link/ontology#spatialCloseMatch → 0 references	

Florian Thiery, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

via <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/wiki/Item:Q74>

has coordinate

51°53'37.3"N, 8°29'32.6"W

certainty level High

certainty description on-site survey at exhibition area

method used on-site survey

acting person Florian Thiery

source type (detail) on-site survey (source type)

source type (generic) on-site survey (source type)

method description on-site survey at UCC Cork

precision ±0.0001°

location type Exhibition Site

point type Exhibition

→ 0 references

51°48'59.58"N, 8°45'57.13"W

certainty level

certainty description

Low

Gippert/Web, Ogham 81:
 "According to Brash, JRSAI 10, 1869, 260, the stone was found in a structure called Rath Lisheenagreine, in the townland of Gurrans (sic!), parish of Templemartin, 1 mile. north of the parish church (the village in question is named "Gurrans" in the Cork U.C. too). A detailed map of the rath (in connection with the larger Rath Lisnacaheragh) is available in S.P. O' R'Yordain's article in PRIA 47-C, 1941-42, 77 ff. - According to Brash, the stone was discovered by one farmer Crowley 17 years before (the publication of his article in JRSAI 10, 1869); Macalister states in CIIC that it "has been known since the sixties" and "appears to have come from a souterrain in the group" of "earth-works" on the townland of Gurrans. The first report was made by John Lyons, C.C., Newcestown, Enniskeane; Brash's visit took place on 16.12.1868. The stone was moved to the Museum of the U.C., Cork after Macalister first visited it (at that time it was still "standing loosely in one of the ditches": CIIC 1, 84). In the collection of the U.C., it is assigned no. 17."

method used

acting person

source type (generic)

source type (detail)

method description

precision

location type

point type

Georeferencing

Florian Thiery

Textual Description

Paper

found in old documents

±0.0001°

Findspot

Location of a Place as a Concept

fuzzy-sl Wikibase [Q74]

Define SPARQL query service

```
import os
from SPARQLWrapper import SPARQLWrapper, JSON
import pandas as pd
import geopandas as gpd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from shapely.geometry import Point
import contextily as ctx # For adding OpenStreetMap basemaps
from matplotlib.patches import Patch
from scipy.stats import gaussian_kde
import numpy as np

def querySparql(query):
    sparql = SPARQLWrapper("https://query.wikidata.org/sparql")
    sparql.setQuery(query)
    sparql.setReturnFormat(JSON)
    results = sparql.queryAndConvert()
    return results['results']['bindings']

# Define the GeoJSON file path
geojson_file = os.path.join(os.getcwd(), "gs_ireland_island.geojson") # Adjusted for Jupyter
```

Define the SPARQL Query

```
# SPARQL Query
oghamQuery = """
SELECT ?item ?itemLabel ?geo ?site ?siteLabel ?county ?countyLabel WHERE {
  ?item wdt:P31 wd:Q804647.
  ?item wdt:P189 ?site.
  ?site wdt:P31 wd:Q72617071.
  ?item wdt:P189 ?county.
  ?county wdt:P31 wd:Q739872.
  ?item wdt:P625 ?geo.
  SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "en" . }
}
"""
```

Fetch Data and Convert to DataFrame

```
# Fetch data using the SPARQL query
sparql_results = querySparql(oghamQuery)

# Convert SPARQL JSON results into a DataFrame
data = []
for result in sparql_results:
    geo = result['geo']['value'] if 'geo' in result else None
    lat, lon = (None, None)
    if geo:
        lon, lat = map(float, geo.replace("Point(", "").replace(")", "").split(","))
    data.append({
        "item": result['item']['value'],
        "itemLabel": result['itemLabel']['value'],
        "site": result['site']['value'],
        "siteLabel": result['siteLabel']['value'],
        "county": result['county']['value'],
        "countyLabel": result['countyLabel']['value'],
        "latitude": lat,
        "longitude": lon,
    })
df = pd.DataFrame(data)
df
```

Visualise the Data as Maps

```
# Check if DataFrame is populated
if df.empty:
    print("No data retrieved from the query.")
else:
    # Filter rows with valid coordinates
    df_with_coords = df.dropna(subset=['latitude', 'longitude'])

    # Create a GeoDataFrame
    gdf = gpd.GeoDataFrame(
        df_with_coords,
        geometry=[Point(xy) for xy in zip(df_with_coords['longitude'], df_with_coords['latitude'])],
        crs="EPSG:4326"
    )

    # Convert to Web Mercator for OSM basemap
    gdf_mercator = gdf.to_crs(epsg=3857)

    # Load Ireland boundary from GeoJSON
    ireland_boundary = gpd.read_file(geojson_file)
    ireland_boundary = ireland_boundary.to_crs(epsg=3857)

    # Map 1: Plot points without text decorations
    fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 8))
    gdf_mercator.plot(ax=ax, color='red', markersize=50, alpha=0.7, label='ogham sites')
    ctx.add_basemap(ax, source=ctx.providers.OpenStreetMap.Mapnik, zoom=8)
    ax.set_axis_off()
    plt.title("Map of Ogham Stone Sites (OSM)")
    plt.legend()
    plt.show()

    # Map 2: Plot with points colored by county and fix legend
    fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 8))
    unique_counties = gdf['countyLabel'].unique()
    colors = plt.cm.tab20.colors[:len(unique_counties)] # Generate unique colors
    county_colors = {county: colors[idx] for idx, county in enumerate(unique_counties)}

    patches = []
    for county, color in county_colors.items():
        county_data = gdf_mercator[gdf_mercator['countyLabel'] == county]
        county_data.plot(ax=ax, color=color, markersize=50, alpha=0.7)
        patches.append(Patch(color=color, label=county)) # Add patch for legend

    ctx.add_basemap(ax, source=ctx.providers.OpenStreetMap.Mapnik, zoom=8)
    ax.set_axis_off()
    plt.title("Map of Ogham Stone Sites Grouped by Counties")
    plt.legend(handles=patches, title="Counties", bbox_to_anchor=(1.05, 1), loc='upper left')
    plt.show()

    # Map 3: Density map with normalized values
    x = gdf_mercator.geometry.x
    y = gdf_mercator.geometry.y

    # Calculate kernel density
    xy = np.vstack([x, y])
    kde = gaussian_kde(xy)
    density = kde(xy)

    # Normalize density to range [0, 1]
    density_normalized = (density - density.min()) / (density.max() - density.min())
    gdf_mercator['density'] = density_normalized

    fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 8))
    ireland_boundary.plot(ax=ax, color="white", edgecolor="black")
    gdf_mercator.plot(ax=ax, column='density', cmap="Reds", markersize=50, alpha=0.7, legend=True)
    ctx.add_basemap(ax, source=ctx.providers.OpenStreetMap.Mapnik, zoom=8)
    ax.set_axis_off()
    plt.title("Density Map of Ogham Stone Sites (Normalized)")
    plt.show()
```


	item	itemLabel	site	siteLabel	county	countyLabel	latitude	longitude
0	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892459	CIIC 71 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85394002	Ahalisky (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.678889	-8.846944
1	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892460	CIIC 72 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85394004	Aultagh (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.770833	-9.088056
2	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892463	CIIC 73 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393926	Carhoovauler (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.688333	-8.956111
3	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892466	CIIC 74 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393926	Carhoovauler (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.688333	-8.956111
4	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892468	CIIC 75 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393928	Keenrath (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.759444	-9.185833
...
328	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892620	CIIC 156 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111
329	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892623	CIIC 157 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111
330	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892626	CIIC 158 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111
331	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892629	CIIC 159 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111
332	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892630	CIIC 160 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111

333 rows x 8 columns

via <https://research-squirrel-engineers.github.io/jupyter-nb-lod/wikidata-ogham-sites-map>

Wikidata

Map of Ogham Stone Sites (OSM)

- Main page
- Community portal
- Project chat
- Create a new item
- Recent changes
- Random item
- Query Service
- Neatly
- Help
- Donate
- Lexicographical data
- Create a new Lexeme
- Recent changes
- Random Lexeme
- Tools
- What links here
- Related changes
- Special pages
- Permanent link
- Page information
- Concise URL
- Cite this page
- Get shortened URL
- Download QR code

Item [Discussion](#)

Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV (Q130529871)

Ogham Stone #4 in the University College Cork Stone Corridor

Q130529871 edit

→ In more languages

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	Ogham Stone #4 in the University College Cork Stone Corridor	Q130529871
German	No label defined	No description defined	
French	No label defined	No description defined	
Bavarian	No label defined	No description defined	

All entered languages

Statements

Instance of

- ogham stone edit
 - 0 references + add reference
- Ogham Stone Semantic Concept edit
 - 0 references + add reference
- archaeological artifact edit
 - 0 references

Identifiers

FactGrid item ID Q1000294 edit

- 0 references

Irish Sites and Monuments Record ID CO074-148---- edit

- 0 references

OpenStreetMap node ID 11071361392 edit

- 0 references

Wikidata [Q130529871]

Density Map of Ogham Stone Sites (Normalized)

Item Discussion

Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV (Q1247)

3D model of the Ogham Stone #4 in the University College Cork Stone Corridor

edit

▼ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	3D model of the Ogham Stone #4 in the University College Cork Stone Corridor	
British English	No label defined	No description defined	

► Mapping to other ontologies

Predicate	URL	
		+ add mapping

Statements

instance of	Media item	edit
	▼ 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

license	Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike	edit
	▼ 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

has technique	Photogrammetry	edit
---------------	-----------------------------	-------------------

file view

<https://semantic-kompakkt.de/entity/670e54210da6ec51ee08e5fb>

Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV

3D model of the Ogham Stone #4 in the University College Cork Stone Corridor

Related agents

Rightsowner: [University College Cork \(UCC\)](#)Data Creator: [Anne-Karoline Distel](#)Creator: [Anne-Karoline Distel](#)Editor: [Florian Thierj](#)Contact Person: [Florian Thierj](#)

Licence

Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International (CC BY-NC-SA 4.0)

Creation

Technique: [Photogrammetry](#)Software: [KIRI engine](#)

Equipment: Smartphone

Date: Invalid Date

Related object structure

[Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV](#)

cassittas (Q1013406)

a person mentioned in an inscription on an Ogham Stone

▼ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description
English	cassittas	a person mentioned in an inscription on an Ogham Stone

Item Discussion

C[A]SSITT[A]S Annotation (CIIC 81) (Q1255)

Person in C[A]SSITT[A]S MAQI MUQOI CALLITI

▼ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description
English	C[A]SSITT[A]S Annotation (CIIC 81)	Person in C[A]SSITT[A]S MAQI MUQOI CALLITI

Main page
Recent changes
Random page
Help about MediaWiki

Wikibase
New item

Semantic Kompakkt [Q1247]

Main page
Query service
Sample queries
Advanced text search
Recent changes

Browse
FactGrid Viewer
Knowledge Browser
EntTree genealogies

Project Spaces
Blog
Projects historically
Projects alphabetically
Projects personally
To Do
SPARQL Lab

Items & Properties
New Item
Merge items
Batch fragments
QuickStatements
Directory of Properties
New Property
Data modeling
Help

Lexemes

New Lexeme
Search

Tools

What links here
Related changes
Special pages
Printable version
Permanent link
Page information
Concept URI

Item Discussion

Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV (Q1000294)

Ogham Stone #4 in the University College Cork Stone Corridor

↕ In more languages

Language	Label	Description
English	Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	Ogham Stone #4 in the University College Cork Stone Corridor
British English	No label defined	No description defined

Statements

Instance of	Ogham Stone	↕ 0 references
Research projects that contributed to this data set	The FactGrid Ogham Project (2024-)	↕ 0 references
Language	Ogham	↕ 0 references
Genre classification	Ogham Stone	↕ 0 references
Script style	Ogham	↕ 0 references

inscription	C[A]SSITT[A]S MAQI MUCCI CALLITI	↕ 0 references
Persons mentioned	cassittas	↕ 0 references
	Calliti	↕ 0 references
Things mentioned	MAQI	↕ 0 references
	MUCCI	↕ 0 references
	MUCCI	↕ 0 references

cassittas (Q1013406)

a person mentioned in an inscription on an Ogham Stone

↕ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description
English	cassittas	a person mentioned in an inscription on an Ogham Stone

Calliti (Q1013407)

a person mentioned in an inscription on an Ogham Ston

↕ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description
English	Calliti	a person mentioned in an inscription on an Ogham Ston

MAQI (Q1013408)

son

MAQ | MAC | /-#- | MACCI | MAQI | MACV | MACI

↕ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	MAQI	son	MAQ MAC /-#- MACCI MAQI MACV MACI

MUCCI (Q1013410)

túath, tribe

/-#- | MACCU | MOCU | MOCCI | MOCO

↕ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	MUCCI	túath, tribe	/-#- MACCU MOCU MOCCI MOCO

Ausführen Teilen Export Wizard Speichern Laden Einstellungen Hilfe overpass turbo Karte Daten

```

1 /*
2 This is an example Overpass query.
3 Try it out by pressing the Run button above!
4 You can find more examples with the Load tool.
5 */
6 node
7 [historic=ogham_stone]
8 {{bbox}};
9 out;

```

```

<node id="5145413640" lat="52.1102476" lon="-10.4731913">
  <tag k="historic" v="ogham_stone"/>
  <tag k="inscription" v="ERC MAQI MAQI-ERCIAS MU DOVINIA"/>
  <tag k="moved" v="no"/>
  <tag k="name" v="CIIC 178"/>
  <tag k="project" v="ogham.link"/>
  <tag k="ref:IE:smr" v="KE052-059002-"/>
  <tag k="source" v="survey"/>
  <tag k="wikidata" v="Q70892682"/>
  <tag k="wikimedia_commons" v="File:Coumeenoole_Ogham_Stone_(Dunmore_Head).jpg"/>
</node>

```

Node 5145413640

Tags

- historic = ogham_stone
- inscription = ERC MAQI MAQI-ERCIAS MU DOVINIA
- moved = no
- name = CIIC 178
- project = ogham.link
- ref:IE:smr = KE052-059002-
- source = survey
- wikidata = Q70892682
- wikimedia_commons = File:Coumeenoole_Ogham_Stone_(Dunmore_Head).jpg

Coordinates:
52.1102476 / -10.4731913 (latlon)

geladen – Nodes: 7, Ways: 0, Relations: 0
angezeigt – POIs: 7, Linien: 0, Polygone: 0

Leaflet | © OpenStreetMap contributors
geladen – Nodes: 106, Ways: 0, Relations: 0
angezeigt – POIs: 106, Linien: 0, Polygone: 0

Floriani Thierry, CC BY 4.0, via [Wikimedia Commons](#)

via <https://overpass-turbo.eu/s/1lwq>

OpenStreetMap [Overpass-Turbo]

THX to
Lozana !!!

Federating between *Semantic Kompakkt* to get the 3D file view location & *Wikidata* to get all external IDs

Wikibase / Query Service Examples

Query Helper

+ Filter

object of representation

+ Show

file view

wikidata id

Limit

[Query source](#)

```
1 PREFIX wd: <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/>
2 PREFIX wdt: <http://www.wikidata.org/prop/direct/>
3 PREFIX wdqs: <https://query.wikidata.org/sparql>
4
5 SELECT DISTINCT ?CIIC81Label ?3D_view ?wd_id ?OSM_id ?SMRS_id ?LOD_id ?Factgrid_id WHERE {
6   SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "[AUTO_LANGUAGE],en". }
7   VALUES ?CIIC81 {tib:Q1407}
8   ?Media_item tibt:P63 ?CIIC81.
9   ?Media_item tibt:P74 ?3D_view.
10  ?CIIC81 tibt:P107 ?wd_id.
11
12  BIND(IRI(CONCAT(STR(wd:), ?wd_id)) AS ?wd_item)
13
14  SERVICE wdqs: {
15    ?wd_item wdt:P11693 ?OSM_id;
16    wdt:P4057 ?SMRS_id;
17    wdt:P2888 ?LOD_id;
18    wdt:P8168 ?Factgrid_id.
19  }
20 }
21
```

CIIC81Label	3D_view	wd_id	OSM_id	SMRS_id	LOD_id	Factgrid_id
Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	https://semantic-kompakkt.de/entity/670e542110da6ec51ee08e5fb	Q130529871	11071361392	CO074-148----	http://lod.ogham.link/data/Y50000081	Q1000294

Federating between *Semantic Kompakkt* (as starting point), *Wikidata* (to get external IDs), *FactGrid* (to get Fuzzy-SL ID), and *Fuzzy Spatial Locations* (*fuzzy-sl*) to get coordinates*

*NB: Not possible out of the box – requires additional config of the allowlist & relatively complex syntax, prone to mistakes when writing manually

[Query source](#)

THX to Lozana !!!

Wikibase / Query Service Examples

```

1 PREFIX wd: <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/>
2 PREFIX wdt: <http://www.wikidata.org/prop/direct/>
3 PREFIX wdqs: <https://query.wikidata.org/>
4 PREFIX fslwd: <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/entity/>
5 PREFIX fslwdt: <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/prop/direct/>
6 PREFIX fg: <https://database.factgrid.de/entity/>
7 PREFIX fgt: <https://database.factgrid.de/prop/direct/>
8
9 SELECT DISTINCT ?CIIC81Label ?3D_view ?wd_id ?OSM_id ?SMRS_id ?LOD_id
10 ?Factgrid_id ?fuzzy_id ?coordinates WHERE {
11 SERVICE wikibase:label {
12 bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "[AUTO_LANGUAGE],en". }
13 VALUES ?CIIC81 {tib:Q1407}
14 ?Media_item tib:P63 ?CIIC81.
15 ?Media_item tib:P74 ?3D_view.
16 ?CIIC81 tib:P107 ?wd_id.
17
18 BIND(IRI(CONCAT(STR(wd:), ?wd_id)) AS ?wd_item)
19
20 SERVICE wdqs: {
21 ?wd_item wdt:P11693 ?OSM_id;
22 wdt:P4057 ?SMRS_id;
23 wdt:P2888 ?LOD_id;
24 wdt:P8168 ?Factgrid_id.
25 }
26
27 BIND(IRI(CONCAT(STR(fg:), ?Factgrid_id)) AS ?Factgrid_item)
28 SERVICE <https://database.factgrid.de/sparql> {
29 ?Factgrid_item fgt:P1215 ?fuzzy_id.
30 }
31
32 BIND(IRI(CONCAT(STR(fslwd:), ?fuzzy_id)) AS ?fuzzy_item)
33 SERVICE <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/query/sparql> {
34 ?fuzzy_item fslwdt:P4 ?coordinates.
35 }
36 }
37

```

1 result in 520 ms

CIIC81Label	3D_view	wd_id	OSM_id	SMRS_id	LOD_id	Factgrid_id	fuzzy_id	coordinates
Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	<https://semantic-kompakkt.de/entity/670e54210da6ec51ee08e5fb>	Q130529871	11071361392	CO074-148---	<http://lod.ogham.link/data/Y50000081>	Q1000294	Q74	Point(-8.492443111 51.893659305)

CIIC81Label	3D_view	wd_id	OSM_id	SMRS_id	LOD_id	Factgrid_id	fuzzy_id	coordinates
Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	<https://semantic-kompakkt.de/entity/670e54210da6ec51ee08e5fb>	Q130529871	11071361392	CO074-148---	<http://lod.ogham.link/data/Y50000081>	Q1000294	Q74	Point(-8.492443111 51.893659305)

Campanian Ignimbrite

Ashes & Archaeological Network

About 40'000 years ago, the largest eruption of the Campanian Ignimbrite (CI) took place in the Phlegraean Fields.

Findspots with **spatial-type: Cave** and **Archaeological Site**

Figure 7. Selection of retouched bladelets from 'rsa' and 'gic'. Additional photos of retouched bladelets from gic and rsa can be found in Supplementary Figs. S14-S15. The number following the alphabetical list corresponds to the ID assigned by AF during the techno-typological analysis (refer to the provided dataset for details). Tools are sorted by the position of the retouch: direct: bilateral retouch (a, c-f, h-p, s, and v), direct unilateral (b, g, and u), inverse (q), and alternate (r and t). Photos by A. Falucci.

Falucci, Armando, Simona Arrighi, Vincenzo Spagnolo, Matteo Rossini, Owen Alexander Higgins, Brunella Muttillo, Ivan Martini, et al. 2024. 'A Pre-Campanian Ignimbrite Techno-Cultural Shift in the Aurignacian Sequence of Grotta Di Castelcivita, Southern Italy'. *Scientific Reports* 14 (1): 12783. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-59896-6>

Oertle, Annette, Jacopo Czezzini, Adriana Moroni, Annamaria Ronchitelli, Stefano Benazzi, Armando Falucci, Giulia Marciani, et al. 2025. 'New Insights from the Application of ZooMS to Late Pleistocene Fauna from Grotta Di Castelcivita, Southern Italy'. *Scientific Reports* 15 (1): 25906. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-11355-6>

Fig. 5. Newly identified taxa from originally unidentified fragmented bones. (a) CLE0043 Canid from spH 14. (b) CLE036 Canid from spH 38. (c) CLE072 Urocyon from spH 27. (d) CLE048 Urocyon from spH 28. (e) CLE054 Urocyon from spH 38. (f) CLE076 Rhinoceros from spH 24. (g) CLE050 Rhinoceros from spH 25.

<https://www.openstreetmap.org/node/337519639>

Castelcivita Cave in literature and OpenStreetMap

Castelcivita Cave EN

http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/cisite_5

The Castelcivita Cave resource is powered by Static GeoPubby generated using the SPARQLing Unicorn OGIS Plugin

Search: Download Options: Format: Turtle (TTL)

Description: comment:CI findspot related from literature

Description: scopeNote:CI findspot related from literature

Property	Value
certaintyDesc (fsl:certaintyDesc)	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper (rdf:langString) (iso639:en)
certaintyLevel (fsl:certaintyLevel)	high (fsl:high) [x]
hasReference (fsl:hasReference)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fedele et al., 2008 (rdf:string) Giaccio et al., 2008 (xsd:string)
partOf (fsl:partOf)	CampanianIgnimbriteProject (fsl:CampanianIgnimbriteProject) [x]
siteType (fsl:siteType)	ArchaeologicalSite (fsl:ArchaeologicalSite) [x]
spatialType (fsl:spatialType)	Cave (fsl:Cave) [x]
hasGeometry (gsp:hasGeometry)	cisite_5_geom (fsl:cisite_5_geom)
type (rdf:type)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Entity (prov:Entity) [x] Place (fsl:Place) [x] Site (fsl:Site) [x]
comment (rdfs:comment)	CI findspot related from literature (rdf:langString) (iso639:en)
label (rdfs:label)	Castelcivita Cave (rdf:langString) (iso639:en)
closeMatch (skos:closeMatch)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 337519639 (337519639) [x] Q3777120 (wikidata:Q3777120) [x]
prefLabel (skos:prefLabel)	Castelcivita Cave (rdf:langString) (iso639:en)
scopeNote (skos:scopeNote)	CI findspot related from literature (rdf:langString) (iso639:en)
is member (rdfs:member) of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Entity instances Collection (fsl:Entity_collection) Place instances Collection (fsl:Place_collection) Site instances Collection (fsl:Site_collection)
is used (prov:used) of	cisite_5_activity (fsl:cisite_5_activity)

Item Discussion

Castelcivita Cave (Q117)

Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot

In more languages

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
Italian	Castelcivita		
English	Castelcivita Cave	Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot	

Statements

instance of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Geological Site Archaeological Site
part of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Campanian Ignimbrite Findspots
has spatial type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cave
has reference	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fedele et al., 2008 Giaccio et al., 2008
has spatial category	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Archaeology Geology
has coordinate	<p>45°29'44.27"N 15°12'23.1"E</p> <p>certainty level: High</p> <p>certainty description: findspot mentioned in a scientific paper and found on OpenStreetMap</p> <p>method used: GeoReferencing</p> <p>acting person: Flora Schenk</p> <p>source type (generic): Textual Description</p> <p>source type (detail): Paper</p> <p>method description: CI findspot related from literature at 0001"</p> <p>precision: findspot</p> <p>location type: findspot</p> <p>point type: Natural Place</p> <p>+ 1 reference</p> <p>reference (string): Fedele et al., 2008</p> <p>Giaccio et al., 2008</p>

Castelcivita Cave in the LOD Cloud

Fig. 3. Grotta Paglicci; Flint industry.

<https://www.openstreetmap.org/node/2293681037>

OpenStreetMap

Node: Grotta Paglicci (2293681037)

Version #7

removed site_type= as transitional simultaneous tagging with archaeological_site=, as discussed in <https://community.openstreetmap.org/t/implementation-of-new-tagging-scheme-of-archaeological-site/7050>

Edited over 2 years ago by ChillyDL
 ChangeSet #138536810
 Location: 41.6541150, 15.6149763

Tags

access	no
archaeological_site	rock_painting
historic	archaeological_site
historiccivilization	prehistoric
name	Grotta Paglicci
wikidata	Q3777010
wikipedia	it:Grotta Paglicci

Download XML

Node / History / Versions:

1 2 3 4 5 6

Zorzi, F. 1964. 'Palaeolithic Discoveries in the Grotta Paglicci'. *Antiquity* 38 (149): 38-44. doi: [10.1017/S0003598X00068757](https://doi.org/10.1017/S0003598X00068757)
 © Published online by Cambridge University Press

Paglicci Cave in literature and OpenStreetMap

Paglicci Cave EN

http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/cisite_19

The **Paglicci Cave** resource is powered by Static **GeoPubby** generated using the **SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin**

Search: Format:

Description: comment:CI findspot related from literature

Description: scopeNote:CI findspot related from literature

Property	Value
certaintyDesc (fsl:certaintyDesc)	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper (rdf:langString) (so6391en)
certaintyLevel (fsl:certaintyLevel)	medium (fsl:medium) [x]
hasReference (fsl:hasReference)	Giaccio et al., 2008 (xsd:string)
partOf (fsl:partOf)	CampanianIgnimbriteProject (fsl:CampanianIgnimbriteProject) [x]
siteType (fsl:siteType)	ArchaeologicalSite (fsl:ArchaeologicalSite) [x]
spatialType (fsl:spatialType)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ArchaeologicalSite (fsl:ArchaeologicalSite) [x] Cave (fsl:Cave) [x]
hasGeometry (gsp:hasGeometry)	cisite_19_geom (fsl:cisite_19_geom)
type (rdf:type)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Entity (prov:Entity) [x] Place (pl:shades:Place) [x] Site (fsl:Site) [x]
comment (rdfs:comment)	CI findspot related from literature (rdf:langString) (so6391en)
label (rdfs:label)	Paglicci Cave (rdf:langString) (so6391en)
closeMatch (skos:closeMatch)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2293681037 (2293681037) [x] Q3777010 (wikidata:Q3777010) [x]
prefLabel (skos:prefLabel)	Paglicci Cave (rdf:langString) (so6391en)
scopeNote (skos:scopeNote)	CI findspot related from literature (rdf:langString) (so6391en)
is member (rdfs:member) of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Entity Instances Collection (fsl:Entity_collection) Place Instances Collection (fsl:Place_collection) Site Instances Collection (fsl:Site_collection)
is used (prov:used) of	cisite_19_activity (fsl:cisite_19_activity)

Item Discussion

Paglicci Cave (Q114)

Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot

in other languages

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
British English	No label defined	No description defined	
English	Paglicci Cave	Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot	

Statements

instance of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Geological Site 0 references Archaeological Site 0 references
part of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Campanian Ignimbrite Findspots 0 references
has spatial type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cave 0 references
has reference	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Giaccio et al., 2008 0 references
has spatial category	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Archaeology 0 references Geology 0 references
has coordinate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 41°39'14.87"N, 15°36'54.0"E certainty level: Medium certainty description: Findspot mentioned in a scientific paper and found on OpenStreetMap method used: Georeferencing acting person: Flavia Schenk source type (generic): Textual Description source type (detail): Paper method description: CI findspot related from literature precision: ±0.0001° location type: Findspot point type: Natural Place 1 reference reference (String): Giaccio et al., 2008

Paglicci Cave in the LOD Cloud

Zde, CC BY-SA 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons

Zde, CC BY-SA 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons

Xalaros, Attribution, via Wikimedia Commons

<http://www.openstreetmap.org/node/1221172611>

Open Street Map Contributors, ODbL

historic	archaeological_site
name:en	Franchthi Cave
wikidata	Q1441331
wikipedia	en:Franchthi Cave

Franchthi Cave as Archaeological Site in the LOD Cloud

Franchthi Cave (Greece) ^{EN}

http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/cisite_45

The Franchthi Cave (Greece) resource is powered by Static [GeoPubby](#) generated using the [SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin](#)

Search: Download options: Format: Turtle (TTL)

Description: comment:CI findspot related from literature

Description: scopeNote:CI findspot related from literature

Property	Value
<code>certaintyDesc</code> (fsi:certaintyDesc)	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper and found on OpenStreetMap (rdf:langstring) (iso6391:en)
<code>certaintyLevel</code> (fsi:certaintyLevel)	high (fsi:high) [x]
<code>hasReference</code> (fsi:hasReference)	Fedele et al., 2003 (xsd:string)
<code>partOf</code> (fsi:partOf)	CampanianIgnimbriteProject (fsi:CampanianIgnimbriteProject) [x]
<code>siteType</code> (fsi:siteType)	archaeologicalSite (fsi:ArchaeologicalSite) [x]
<code>spatialType</code> (fsi:spatialType)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ArchaeologicalSite (fsi:ArchaeologicalSite) [x] Cave (fsi:Cave) [x]
<code>hasGeometry</code> (gsp:hasGeometry)	cisite_45_geom (fsi:cisite_45_geom)
<code>type</code> (rdf:type)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Entity (prov:Entity) [x] Place (placides:Place) [x] Site (fsi:Site) [x]
<code>comment</code> (rdfs:comment)	CI findspot related from literature (rdf:langstring) (iso6391:en)
<code>label</code> (rdfs:label)	Franchthi Cave (Greece) (rdf:langstring) (iso6391:en)
<code>closeMatch</code> (skos:closeMatch)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 122172811 (122172811) [x] Q1444331 (wikidata:Q1444331) [x]
<code>prefLabel</code> (skos:prefLabel)	Franchthi Cave (Greece) (rdf:langstring) (iso6391:en)
<code>scopeNote</code> (skos:scopeNote)	CI findspot related from literature (rdf:langstring) (iso6391:en)
<code>is member of</code> (rdfs:member) of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Entity instances collection (fsi:Entity_collection) Place instances collection (fsi:Place_collection) Site instances collection (fsi:Site_collection)
<code>is used by</code> (prov:used by) of	cisite_45_activity (fsi:cisite_45_activity)

Item Discussion

Franchthi Cave (Q111)

Companion Ignimbrite Findspot

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
British English	No label defined	No description defined	
English	Franchthi Cave	Companion Ignimbrite Findspot	

Statements

instance of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Geological Site Archaeological Site
part of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Campanian Ignimbrite Findspots
has spatial type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cave
has reference	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fedele et al., 2003
has spatial category	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Archaeology Geology
has coordinate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 37°29'21.47N, 23°7'52.07E <p>certainty level: High</p> <p>findspot mentioned in a scientific paper and found on OpenStreetMap</p> <p>method used: Georeferencing</p> <p>writing person: Fiona Schenk</p> <p>instance type (literal): Textual Description</p> <p>source type (literal): Paper</p> <p>method description: CI findspot related from literature</p> <p>precision: ±0.0001°</p> <p>location type: Findspot</p> <p>point type: NotLuzr Place</p> <p>+ 1 reference</p>
WKT Geometry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Point(31.131 37.422) <p>+ 0 references</p>

Franchthi Cave in the LOD Cloud

via trentu.ca

Roland Sore, via flickr rolabin/30105173063

Fig. 14.9. Examples of cutmarks observed on specimens taxa other than ungulates at Crvena Stijena: a) mammoth mandible (M5); b) horse distal tibia (M1); c) *Ursus* sp. metapodial fragment (XXIV); d) *Ursus* sp. fifth metacarpal fragment (M1).

via <http://www.openstreetmap.org/node/10879170567>

Open Street Map Contributors, ODbL

archaeological_site	megalith
historic	archaeological_site
historic:civilization	neolithic
name	Crvena stijena
name:en	Red wall
wikidata	Q121418883
wikipedia	https://bs.wikipedia.org/wiki/Crvena_stijena_(Crna_Gora)

Crvena Stiljena Cave as Archaeological Site in the LOD Cloud

Crvena Stiljena (Montenegro) ^{EN}

http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/cisite_51

The Crvena Stiljena (Montenegro) resource is powered by Static [GeoPubby](#) generated using the [SPARQLing Unicorn OGIS Plugin](#)

Search: Download Options: Format: [Turtle \(TTL\)](#)

Description: comment:CI findspot related from literature

Description: scope:note:CI findspot related from literature

Property	value
certaintyDesc (fsl:certaintyDesc)	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper and found on OpenStreetMap (rdf:langString) (iso639:en)
certaintyLevel (fsl:certaintyLevel)	high (fsl:high) [x]
hasReference (fsl:hasReference)	Morley & Woodward, 2011 (xsd:string)
partOf (fsl:partOf)	CampanianIgnimbriteProject (fsl:CampanianIgnimbriteProject) [x]
siteType (fsl:siteType)	ArchaeologicalSite (fsl:ArchaeologicalSite) [x]
spatialType (fsl:spatialType)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ArchaeologicalSite (fsl:ArchaeologicalSite) [x] Cave (fsl:Cave) [x]
hasGeometry (gsp:hasGeometry)	cisite_51_geom (fsl:cisite_51_geom)
type (rdf:type)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Entity (prov:Entity) [x] Place (fsl:Place) [x] Site (fsl:Site) [x]
comment (rdfs:comment)	CI findspot related from literature (rdf:langString) (iso639:en)
label (rdfs:label)	Crvena Stiljena (Montenegro) (rdf:langString) (iso639:en)
closeMatch (skos:closeMatch)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 10879170567 (10879170567) [x] Q121418883 (wikidata:Q121418883) [x]
prefLabel (skos:prefLabel)	Crvena Stiljena (Montenegro) (rdf:langString) (iso639:en)
scopeNote (skos:scopeNote)	CI findspot related from literature (rdf:langString) (iso639:en)
is member of (rdfs:member) of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Entity instances collection (fsl:Entity_collection) Place instances collection (fsl:Place_collection) Site instances collection (fsl:Site_collection)
is used (prov:used) of	cisite_51_activity (fsl:cisite_51_activity)

- [Main page](#)
- [Recent changes](#)
- [Random page](#)
- [Help about Wikibase](#)
- Tools
- [What links here](#)
- [Recent changes](#)
- [Special pages](#)
- [Printable version](#)
- [Permanent link](#)
- [Page information](#)
- [Concept URI](#)
- Wikibase
- [New item](#)
- [New Property](#)
- [New Schema](#)
- [All Properties](#)
- [Query Service](#)
- [CWLite](#)
- [Data Statements](#)
- In other languages [Add link](#)

Item Discussion (28)

Crvena Stiljena Cave (Q89)

Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot

[+ 0 more languages](#)

[Compare](#)

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
British English	No label defined	No description defined	
English	Crvena Stiljena Cave	Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot	

Statements

Instance of

- Geological Site
 - + 0 references
- Archaeological Site
 - + 0 references

part of

- Campanian Ignimbrite Findspots
 - + 0 references

has spatial type

- Cave
 - + 0 references

has spatial category

- Archaeology
 - + 0 references
- Geology
 - + 0 references

has coordinate

42°46'44.47"N, 18°28'53.47"E	
certainty level	High
certainty description	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper and found on OpenStreetMap
method used	Georeferencing
activity person	Petra Schenk
source type (format)	Tabular Description
source law (label)	Paper
method description	CI findspot related from literature
precision	±0.0001°
location type	Findspot
point type	Natural Place
	+ 1 reference

has reference

- Morley & Woodward, 2011
 - + 0 references

Crvena Stiljena Cave in the LOD Cloud

via <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jasrep.2021.102912> © Tzanova et al.

via <http://www.openstreetmap.org/node/11109379095>

Open Street Map Contributors, ODbL

ele	300
name	Toplitsa Cave
natural	cave_entrance
source_ref	10.1016/j.jasrep.2021.102912
wikidata	Q61788595

Toplitsa Cave as Archaeological Site in the LOD Cloud

Ogham Sites

... with Jupyter Notebooks.

Define SPARQL query service

```
import os
from SPARQLWrapper import SPARQLWrapper, JSON
import pandas as pd
import geopandas as gpd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from shapely.geometry import Point
import contextily as ctx # For adding OpenStreetMap basemaps
from matplotlib.patches import Patch
from scipy.stats import gaussian_kde
import numpy as np

def querySparql(query):
    sparql = SPARQLWrapper("https://query.wikidata.org/sparql")
    sparql.setQuery(query)
    sparql.setReturnFormat(JSON)
    results = sparql.queryAndConvert()
    return results['results']['bindings']

# Define the GeoJSON file path
geojson_file = os.path.join(os.getcwd(), "gs_ireland_island.geojson") # Adjusted for Jupyter Notebook
```

Define the SPARQL Query

```
# SPARQL Query
oghamQuery = """
SELECT ?item ?itemLabel ?geo ?site ?siteLabel ?county ?countyLabel WHERE {
    ?item wdt:P31 wd:Q806167.
    ?item wdt:P189 ?site.
    ?site wdt:P31 wd:Q72617071.
    ?item wdt:P189 ?county.
    ?county wdt:P31 wd:Q179872.
    ?item wdt:P625 ?geo.
    SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "en" . }
}
"""
```

Fetch Data and Convert to DataFrame

```
# Fetch data using the SPARQL query
sparql_results = querySparql(oghamQuery)

# Convert SPARQL JSON results into a DataFrame
data = []

for result in sparql_results:
    geo = result['geo']['value'] if 'geo' in result else None
    lat, lon = (None, None)
    if geo:
        lon, lat = map(float, geo.replace("Point(", "").replace(")", "").split())
        data.append({
            "item": result['item']['value'],
            "itemLabel": result['itemLabel']['value'],
            "site": result['site']['value'],
            "siteLabel": result['siteLabel']['value'],
            "county": result['county']['value'],
            "countyLabel": result['countyLabel']['value'],
            "latitude": lat,
            "longitude": lon,
        })

df = pd.DataFrame(data)
df
```


<https://research-squirrel-engineers.github.io/jupyter-nb-lod/wikidata-ogham-sites-map>

	item	itemLabel	site	siteLabel	county	countyLabel	latitude	longitude
0	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892459	CIIC 71 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85394002	Ahalisky (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.678889	-8.846944
1	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892460	CIIC 72 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85394004	Aultagh (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.770833	-9.088056
2	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892463	CIIC 73 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393926	Carhoovauler (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.688333	-8.956111
3	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892466	CIIC 74 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393926	Carhoovauler (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.688333	-8.956111
4	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892468	CIIC 75 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393928	Keenrath (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.759444	-9.185833
...
328	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892620	CIIC 156 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111
329	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892623	CIIC 157 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111
330	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892626	CIIC 158 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111
331	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892629	CIIC 159 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111
332	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892630	CIIC 160 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111

333 rows × 8 columns

SPARQL query to create DataFrame

Visualise the Data as Maps

```
# Check if DataFrame is populated
if df.empty:
    print("No data retrieved from the query.")
else:
    # Filter rows with valid coordinates
    df_with_coords = df.dropna(subset=['latitude', 'longitude'])

    # Create a GeoDataFrame
    gdf = gpd.GeoDataFrame(
        df_with_coords,
        geometry=[Point(xy) for xy in zip(df_with_coords['longitude'], df_with_coords['latitude'])],
        crs="EPSG:4326"
    )

    # Convert to Web Mercator for OSM basemap
    gdf_mercator = gdf.to_crs(eps=3857)

    # Load Ireland boundary from GeoJSON
    ireland_boundary = gpd.read_file(geojson_file)
    ireland_boundary = ireland_boundary.to_crs(eps=3857)

    # Map 1: Plot points without text decorations
    fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 8))
    gdf_mercator.plot(ax=ax, color='red', markersize=50, alpha=0.7, label="Ogham Stones")
    ctx.add_basemap(ax, source=ctx.providers.OpenStreetMap.Mapnik, zoom=8)
    ax.set_axis_off()
    plt.title("Map of Ogham Stone Sites (OSM)")
    plt.legend()
    plt.show()
```

```
# Map 2: Plot with points colored by county and fix Legend
fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 8))
unique_counties = gdf['countyLabel'].unique()
colors = plt.cm.tab20.colors[:len(unique_counties)] # Generate unique colors
county_colors = {county: colors[idx] for idx, county in enumerate(unique_counties)}

patches = []
for county, color in county_colors.items():
    county_data = gdf_mercator[gdf_mercator['countyLabel'] == county]
    county_data.plot(ax=ax, color=color, markersize=50, alpha=0.7)
    patches.append(Patch(color=color, label=county)) # Add patch for Legend

ctx.add_basemap(ax, source=ctx.providers.OpenStreetMap.Mapnik, zoom=8)
ax.set_axis_off()
plt.title("Map of Ogham Stone Sites Grouped by Counties")
plt.legend(handles=patches, title="Counties", bbox_to_anchor=(1.05, 1), loc='upper left')
plt.show()
```

Map 3: Density map with normalized values

```
x = gdf_mercator.geometry.x
y = gdf_mercator.geometry.y

# Calculate kernel density
xy = np.vstack([x, y])
kde = gaussian_kde(xy)
density = kde(xy)

# Normalize density to range [0, 1]
density_normalized = (density - density.min()) / (density.max() - density.min())
gdf_mercator['density'] = density_normalized

fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 8))
ireland_boundary.plot(ax=ax, color="white", edgecolor="black")
gdf_mercator.plot(ax=ax, column='density', cmap="Reds", markersize=50, alpha=0.7, legend=True)
ctx.add_basemap(ax, source=ctx.providers.OpenStreetMap.Mapnik, zoom=8)
ax.set_axis_off()
plt.title("Density Map of Ogham Stone Sites (Normalized)")
plt.show()
```

Create Maps

Map of Ogham Stone Sites (OSM)

Map of Ogham Stone Sites Grouped by Counties

Density Map of Ogham Stone Sites (Normalized)

Output

Campanian Ignimbrite

... with Jupyter Notebooks.

Define SPARQL query service

```
from SPARQLWrapper import SPARQLWrapper, TURTLE
from rdflib import Graph, Namespace
from rdflib.namespace import RDF, RDFS
import os
from SPARQLWrapper import SPARQLWrapper, JSON
import pandas as pd
import geopandas as gpd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from shapely.geometry import Point
import contextily as ctx # For adding OpenStreetMap basemaps
from matplotlib.patches import Patch
from scipy.stats import gaussian_kde
import numpy as np

# Function to query Solid Pod and retrieve data in TURTLE format
def querySolidPod(sparql_endpoint, query):
    sparql = SPARQLWrapper(sparql_endpoint)
    sparql.setQuery(query)
    sparql.setReturnFormat(TURTLE) # Request Turtle format
    results = sparql.query().convert()
    return results
```

Define the SPARQL Query

```
# SPARQL Query
solid_pod_query = """
SELECT ?item ?geo ?label ?ref ?spatialType {
  ?item a <http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/Site> .
  ?item rdfs:label ?label.
  ?item <http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/hasReference> ?ref .
  ?item <http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/spatialType> ?spatialType .
  ?item <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasGeometry> ?item_geom .
  ?item_geom <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#asWKT> ?geo .
}
"""
```

Fetch Data and Convert to DataFrame

```
sparql_endpoint = "https://fuzzy-sl.solidweb.org/campanian-ignimbrite-geo/ci_full.ttl"

# Query the endpoint
turtle_data = querySolidPod(sparql_endpoint, solid_pod_query)

# Parse Turtle data with rdflib
g = Graph()
g.parse(data=turtle_data, format="turtle")

# Extract namespaces
site_ns = Namespace("http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/")
gs = Namespace("http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#")

# Run the SPARQL query against the loaded Turtle data
results = g.query(solid_pod_query)

# Process the Results into a DataFrame
data = []
for row in results:
    spatial_type = str(row.spatialType).replace("http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/", "")
    geo_str = str(row.geo)
    if geo_str.find("POINT(") != -1:
        geo_str = geo_str.replace("<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326>", "").replace("<POINT(", "").replace(")", "")
    else:
        geo_str = geo_str.replace("<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326>", "")
        geo_str = geo_str.replace(")", "")
        geo_str = geo_str.replace(" POINT (", "")

    lon, lat = map(float, geo_str.split())

    data.append({
        "spatialType": spatial_type,
        "latitude": lat,
        "longitude": lon,
    })

# Convert the data to a pandas DataFrame
df = pd.DataFrame(data)
df
```


<https://research-squirrel-engineers.github.io/jupyter-nb-lod/solidpod-ci>

SPARQL query to create DataFrame

	spatialType	latitude	longitude
0	Sink	40.9489	14.3624
1	UnknownCategory	40.9285	14.6983
2	InhabitedPlace	40.7119	14.7680
3	InhabitedPlace	40.6993	14.5259
4	Cave	40.4956	15.2092
...
98	UnknownCategory	44.9032	20.2802
99	UnknownCategory	44.2462	27.9347
100	UnknownCategory	44.2462	27.9347
101	Lake	40.9167	21.0000
102	Lake	40.9167	21.0000

103 rows × 3 columns

SPARQL query to create DataFrame

Visualise the Data in a bar chart

```
# Check if DataFrame is populated
if not df.empty and 'spatialType' in df:
    # Plot 1: Number of Sites by Spatial Type
    plt.figure(figsize=(12, 8))
    df['spatialType'].value_counts().plot(kind='bar', color='skyblue', edgecolor='black')
    plt.title("Number of Sites by Spatial Type", fontsize=16)
    plt.xlabel("Spatial Type", fontsize=14)
    plt.ylabel("Number of Sites", fontsize=14)
    plt.xticks(rotation=45, ha="right")
    plt.tight_layout()
    plt.show()
else:
    print("No data retrieved or 'spatialType' column is missing.")
```

Visualise the Data in a map

```
# Check if DataFrame is populated
if df.empty:
    print("No data retrieved from the query.")
else:
    # Filter rows with valid coordinates
    df_with_coords = df.dropna(subset=['latitude', 'longitude'])

    # Create a GeoDataFrame
    gdf = gpd.GeoDataFrame(
        df_with_coords,
        geometry=[Point(xy) for xy in zip(df_with_coords['longitude'], df_with_coords['latitude'])],
        crs="EPSG:4326"
    )

    # Convert to Web Mercator for OSM basemap
    gdf_mercator = gdf.to_crs(epsg=3857)

    # Plot points on the map
    fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 8))
    gdf_mercator.plot(ax=ax, color='red', markersize=50, alpha=0.7, label="CI sites")

    # Add OSM basemap
    ctx.add_basemap(ax, source=ctx.providers.OpenStreetMap.Mapnik)

    ax.set_axis_off()
    plt.title("Map of CI sites in Europe")
    plt.legend()
    plt.show()
```

Create Chart & Map

Map of CI sites in Europe

Output

Finis! Thx!

Florian Thiery M.Sc.
Research Squirrel Engineers Network
mail@fthiery.de
ORCID: 0000-0002-3246-3531

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.